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Strengthening Open Responsible Research and Innovation

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The SUPER MoRRI project

Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) aims to transform the research and innovation system by **better aligning it with societal values, needs and concerns**, and by encouraging societal actors to work together during the whole research and innovation cycle. ORRI means to strengthen **public engagement, openness of research (findings), gender equality, ethics and research integrity as well as third mission** in research and innovation.

SUPER MoRRI ("Scientific Understanding and Provision of an Enhanced and Robust Monitoring system for RRI"), a 2019-2024 research project funded by the EU Horizon 2020 SwafS-21 initiative, studied **patterns, pathways and benefits of ORRI practices and policies across Europe and how to support the transformation of the R&I system towards ORRI**.

To this end, SUPER MoRRI conducted an empirical programme comprising of a number of different studies.

Studies on patterns, pathways & benefits

The **Researchers Survey** examined researchers' practices, perceptions of, and attitudes towards ORRI. It addressed ca. 127,000 researchers at 122 higher education institutions in Europe. The net sample was 4,180 respondents.

CCN-RPO study: A country correspondents network (CCN) examined how Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) support different ORRI dimensions. 122 higher education institutions across Europe were analysed according to their strategies and/or policies to include these dimensions. They also looked at the degree of strategic prioritization of different ORRI dimensions, and whether they were described in practical or aspirational terms.

CCN-RFO study: The CCN network also examined ORRI policies in Research Funding Organizations (RFOs) in terms of (1) priority setting mechanism for research funding; (2) development of funding instruments and design; (3) assessment of grant proposals for researchers and projects. The study covered 55 European RFOs.

Six case projects: SUPER MoRRI performed six qualitative in-depth case studies to analyse **pathways** to ORRI in public engagement, ethics and gender equality.

ORRI Patterns

Public Engagement patterns

The Researchers Survey shows that **many researchers involved non-academic actors in their research** at least a few times in the last three years. Non-academic actors include government/agencies, companies/enterprises, citizens, NGOs/CSOs and consumers/patients-groups. However, **chances** for being involved in research are **unevenly distributed** among actor groups:

- government/agencies (67%)
- companies/ enterprises (62%)
- citizens (56%)
- NGOs/CSOs (51%)
- consumer/patient groups (39%).

Researchers perceived **barriers to public engagement** as:

- too time-consuming (74%),
- a lack of institutional incentives (58%),
- not sure how to do public engagement (38%)
- there would be too few benefits of public engagement (37%).

Open Access patterns

Researchers **strongly engaged in open access**. Open publication was a widespread activity adopted by a huge majority of responding researchers.

Barriers to open science were:

- expensive publication fees (84%)
- lack of institutional incentives (53%)
- lack of support (44%)
- time constraints (39%).

75% of RPOs had open science **policies** in place, of which can be categorized as support and incentives (65%), support (7%), aims (4%). Amongst these, open access was most frequent and most strong.

Gender Equality patterns

On average **1/5 of responding researchers considered gender aspects** in each phase of their research projects in the last three years. However, the **share of involvement decreases continuously as research projects advance** from designing to disseminating research.

This pattern is also perceived in the share of respondents that considered gender aspects in “most” and in “a few of their projects”.

In addition, throughout all phases of research, **the share of respondents who do not consider gender aspects is highest**, and this share also increases as research projects progress.

Researchers mentioned **barriers** in gender equality less frequently than in public engagement and open access. These barriers included:

- lack of relevance (45%)
- lack of institutional incentives (32%)
- lack of knowledge (19%)
- lack of benefits (19%).

The CCN-RPO study shows that:

- **63% European RPOs had gender equality support and incentives policies in place** of which 7% are “support” and 10% are “aims”.
- **1/5 of the surveyed RPOs had no gender equality policies** in place.
- Policies in the **sub-area of “culture and behaviour”** were the **most developed** in our sample, policies in other areas were less developed.

Ethics pattern

92% responding researchers mentioned that they **consider ethical issues in their research**. **Other ethic practices** such as submitting research to ethical review (55%) or active participation in training (35%) and reviewing (21%) **were less frequent**.

Respondents mentioned barriers to ethics less frequently compared to public engagement and open science. **Barriers** mentioned are:

- lack of institutional incentives (35%)
- lack of time (24%)
- relevance (22%)
- knowledge (17%).

A huge majority of **86% of RPOs** surveyed in the CCN-RPO study had **support and incentive policies for ethics and integrity** in place, 6% had an “aims policy” and only 8% had no policy.

Research Performing Organisations (RPO) policies patterns

To do ORRI, researchers need support from RPOs. The CCN-RPO survey shows that European RPOs largely have policies to support ORRI. However, these policies are not equally stringent across all dimensions of ORRI.

- Strict support and incentives policies:
 - Ethics and Research Integrity (86%)
 - Open Science (65%)
 - Third Mission (64%)
 - Gender Equality (63%).

- Mature Public Engagement policies are least common (48%) and are otherwise limited to:
 - “support” measures (21%)
 - “no policies” (21%)
 - less developed “aims” (10%)
 - The number of “mature” policies decreases as level of participation increases.

Research Funding Organisations (RFO) policies patterns

Researchers’ ORRI practices also need support from RFOs policies. The CCN-RFO study shows that the **most prevalent ORRI dimension** in RFO documents are: **open science, research integrity and gender equality**. Citizen science, societal impact, innovation pathways and AIRR were mentioned less.

Several surveyed RFOs did not mention individual elements of open science and 15 of them did not mention any elements.

- 29 European RFOs of the 55 covered in the survey had “standard” policies, seven had “spirited” policies and four “integrated” policies.
 - Elements of ORRI most likely considered in RFO’s research assessment are **gender balance in research teams and open science**. However, often research integrity and ethics are fundamental criteria for eligibility.
- 2/3 of RPOs **did not include any ORRI elements in research assessment**, a main mechanism of research funding.
- Broader analysis of findings suggest that it is **not common practice to involve other actors in setting funding priorities** and or in the **development of funding instruments**. 15 RFOs reported they do not involve any of the mentioned stakeholders in priority setting.
- In RFOs that do involve stakeholders, the **range of involved stakeholders is wide and imbalanced** with overrepresentation from industry, the scientific community, civil society organisations and policymakers compared to citizens, patient organizations or other funding organizations.

ORRI Pathways

Analysis of SUPER MoORRI qualitative case studies revealed several common themes.

Cultures in RFOs, RPOs CSOs, business and research disciplines **matter** for ORRI because they can promote and impede ORRI. Thus, existing cultures must be recognized in attempts to promote ORRI.

The translation of ORRI must consider existing **routines** in RFOs, RPOs, CSOs and business and how they might hinder, neglect, or support ORRI. Successful translation of ORRI depends on **informed actors** with the necessary knowledge and networks.

Interdisciplinarity is a **major avenue** to ORRI. The “devil”, however, lies in the details. Without proper cooperation of researchers from different disciplines, interdisciplinarity runs the **risk** that **researchers remain in the comfort zone** of their respective disciplines without actually cooperating

Transdisciplinarity has its **potentials**, but it is even more complex than interdisciplinarity and runs the **risk of remaining tokenistic** when the world of research, stakeholders and publics stay apart, and the self-perceptions and goals of different actors are not properly recognized.

Translations towards ORRI must **consider existing inequalities** that impede ORRI and consider whether **new inequalities** might be generated.

Benefits

The case studies indicate several **potential societal, democratic, scientific, and economic benefits**. The case studies also show several pathway themes which impact the realization of benefits.

Respondents of the **researcher survey** mention several benefits which they either already observed or expected. These are different in scale and kind in different dimensions of ORRI.

- Many responding researchers perceived benefits of **public engagement** activities particularly in the areas of **societal benefits** (higher social relevance, increase societal impact) and **democratic benefits** (recognize citizens' knowledge, empowering citizen).
- However, they also perceived **scientific benefits** (emergence of new topic, higher quality of scientific output) and **economic benefits** (improved products and services, more innovation).
- Researchers observed and expected **scientific benefits** particularly in the area of **Open Science**.
- Benefits experienced and expected from **Gender Equality** in research are in general **lower** than in Public Engagement and Open Science.
- Experiences and expectations from responding researchers about benefits of **ethics** practices related to **scientific** benefits and **societal benefits**. Almost 2/3 of the respondents either observed or expected higher quality in their research; a little more than 50% either observed or expected higher social relevance or societal impact of their research because of ethics practices.

In general, the fact that many respondents still expect benefits from ORRI practices underlines that the generation of **benefits is a long-term process** which is difficult to foresee, plan and measure.

Recommendations

For RPOs and RFOs

- **RPOs and RFOs should support researchers in public engagement.** This includes:
 - increasing **support** and **institutional incentives** that reward these activities.
 - **training researchers** in their **understanding** and **skills** of public engagement.
 - providing **additional staff** for **public engagement activities**, which researchers perceive as time consuming.
 - **exploring** and **showing** the **benefits** of public engagement for research.
- RPOs **without public engagement policies should develop them.** Those RPOs who have only policy in the areas of “aims” and “support”, should **step up their efforts** and define more concrete public engagement policies. RPOs should develop concrete Public Engagement policies particularly in the sub-areas of “public consultation” and “advice and public participation”.
- RFOs should **open their research priority setting** to scientific and societal **stakeholders**, particularly to those which are currently least involved.
- RFOs should **integrate ORRI** elements more strongly in the **assessment** of researchers and research.
- RPOs should **explore** together with researchers the relevance of **gender equality** for research and researchers and work to **expand** and **develop** stringent **policies**, also in areas currently less developed such as “**career advancement**“, “**work-life balance**“, “**women in leadership**“ and “**gender aware science**“.
- **Interdisciplinarity cannot be taken for granted but must be taken seriously.** RPOs and RFOs must encourage, promote, and fund information, training, exchange of good practice and support cooperation amongst researchers from different disciplines. Similar efforts should be made to support **transdisciplinarity** and be aware that transdisciplinarity **remains tokenistic** when researchers, stakeholders and publics stay apart, and the self-perceptions and goals of different actors are not properly recognized and addressed.

For individual researchers

- Researchers should **step up their efforts to involve non-academic actors** in their research. They also should **involve NGOs and consumers** who are currently less involved in research.
- Researchers should **integrate aspects of gender equality** along the **whole research process** from research design, data collection, analysis and dissemination.
- Researchers should not only reflect on the ethical impact of their research by themselves but should also **engage in other practices of “doing” ethics** and integrity in research such as **contributing to the development of standards, participating in training and reviewing**.

For policy makers

- **Cultures** in RFOs, RPOs CSOs, business and research disciplines **matter** for ORRI because they can **promote but also impede** ORRI. Thus, existing cultures **must be recognized** in attempts to promote ORRI. The translation of ORRI must consider existing routines in RFOs, RPOs, CSOs and business and how they might hinder, neglect, or support ORRI.
- **Successful translation** of ORRI depends on **informed actors** with the necessary **knowledge** and **networks**. Thus, **training** about ORRI and **networking** amongst relevant actors must be **promoted**.
- **Translations** towards ORRI **must consider existing inequalities** that impede ORRI and **consider** whether **new inequalities might be generated**. Measures must be taken to overcome such inequalities.

SUPER MoORRI project deliverables on which this policy brief is based can be found under: <https://super-morri.eu/findings/>

